

First schedule of training actions and portfolio of possible contents

Deliverable 1.2

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Summary

Training is an essential element in the systemic innovation chain of B-WaterSmart, anchored in capacity building while corresponding to the stakeholders' needs and expectations.

The B-WaterSmart training portfolio objectives are threefold: dedicated training actions to ensure capacity building on the water-smart solutions and products and maximisation of their value; promote transfer potential and ensure that the products developed meet stakeholder needs and expectations; contribute to the B-WaterSmart dissemination and communication strategy and knowledge portal to ensure knowledge accessibility and uptake.

Besides these planned objectives, the portfolio integrates additional training actions to add value in supporting B-WaterSmart purposes, benefits, and knowledge, both to those directly involved in the project and to a broader public.

This deliverable provides the first schedule of B-WaterSmart training activities and an initial portfolio of contents. As an introduction, chapter 1 presents the role of training in B-WaterSmart and the principles of the training portfolio. Chapters 2 and 3 present the portfolio structure and initial schedule of training actions. Chapter 4 presents the training actions, workflow, and guidance. Chapter 5 presents the planned assessment steps of the training activities and their contribution to key performance indicators. Finally, Annex I outlines the draft content of training actions at level 1 as well as minimum competences / requirements for trainees.

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Dissemination level

- PU = Public
- PP = Restricted to other programme participants
- RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium.
Please specify: _____
- CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

BWS	B-WaterSmart (H2020 funded project)
CoP	Community of Practice
Dx.y	Deliverable y of Work Package x
GA	Grant Agreement
InAll	Innovation Alliance
L1	Level 1 actions
L2	Level 2 actions
L3	Level 3 actions
LL	Living Labs
M	Month
MS	Milestone
T	Task
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

The B-WaterSmart project aims at contributing to water-smart societies and economies by adopting a large-scale systemic approach to select, connect, and demonstrate tailored suites of innovative technology, management, and interoperable smart data solutions for multiple users and sectors. The systemic innovation approach builds on effective collaboration, communication, and knowledge exchange involving six European coastal cities and regions acting as Living Labs (LL) - Alicante, Bodø, Flanders, Lisbon, East Frisia and Venice - and supported by Communities of Practice (CoP) and an Innovation Alliance (InAll). CoP bring together relevant key actors and stakeholders to ensure co-development, acceptance, implementation, and systemic innovation in an interdisciplinary approach, promote mutual learning and incorporate stakeholder knowledge, identify commonalities and gaps between LL while ensuring solution transferability and replicability, and analyse barriers and drivers to innovation growth and market outreach. The InAll implementation aims at the peer-to-peer capacity building by testing and refining the water smartness assessment framework developed by B-WaterSmart and confirming its usability as key to strategic planning towards greater water smartness.

One of the core aims of WP1 - Co-create & demonstrate systemic innovation in six Living Labs is to ensure that the six B-WaterSmart LL are trained to use the project products relevant to their current or foreseen specific context and to optimize the value of the products. This will contribute to maximize the project impact during and beyond the duration of the project. Webinars with partners and other LL stakeholders are the preferred means, complemented by face-to-face training whenever appropriate. WP2 to WP6 will provide the list of topics to be addressed, including the intended timing, learning objectives, preferred means (webinar or face-to-face, and if so, location), responsible person and target audience.

This deliverable provides the first schedule of B-WaterSmart training activities and an initial portfolio of contents. It describes the role of training in B-WaterSmart, the principles of the training portfolio, the portfolio structure, and an initial schedule of training actions.

Annex I outlines the draft content of training actions at level 1 as well as minimum competences / requirements for trainees.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Role of training in BWS

The B-WaterSmart project aims at contributing to water-smart societies and economies by adopting a large-scale systemic approach to select, connect, and show tailored suites of innovative technology, management, and interoperable smart data solutions for multiple users and sectors. The systemic innovation approach builds on effective collaboration, communication and knowledge exchange involving six European coastal cities and regions acting as Living Labs (LL) - Alicante, Bodø, Flanders, Lisbon, East Frisia, and Venice - and supported by Communities of Practise (CoP) and an Innovation Alliance (InAll). CoP bring together relevant key actors and stakeholders to ensure co-development, acceptance, implementation and systemic innovation in an interdisciplinary approach, promote mutual learning and incorporate stakeholder knowledge, recognise commonalities and gaps between LL while ensuring solution transferability and replicability, and analyse barriers and drivers to innovation growth and market outreach. InAll implementation aims at the peer-to-peer capacity building by testing and refining the water smartness assessment framework developed by B-Watersmart, and at showing its usability as key for strategic planning towards greater water smartness.

A core aim of WP1 - Co-create & demonstrate systemic innovation in six Living Labs is to ensure that the six B-WaterSmart LL are trained to use the project products relevant to their current or foreseen specific context and to optimize the value of the products. Webinars with partners and other LL stakeholders are the preferred means, complemented by face-to-face training when appropriate. WP2 to WP6 will provide the list of topics to be addressed, including the topic, intended timing, learning objectives, preferred means (webinar or face-to-face, and if so, the location), responsible person and target audience.

Training is an essential element in the systemic innovation chain of B-WaterSmart, while corresponding to the stakeholders' needs and expectations (Rebelo et al., 2021). Training will contribute to maximize the impact of project work and results during and beyond the project among B-WaterSmart partners, other LL stakeholders and potential followers. With this intent, the training content was designed and planned in close cooperation with the dissemination and exploitation activities in the project.

The BWS training portfolio objectives are threefold:

- Develop dedicated training actions to ensure capacity building on the water-smart solutions and products and optimisation of their value.
- Promote transfer potential and ensure that products correspond to the stakeholders' needs and expectations.
- Contribute to the B-WaterSmart dissemination and communication strategy and knowledge portal to ensure knowledge accessibility and uptake, and to reach actors and stakeholders outside the consortium, as part of the knowledge creation and sharing, training and education aims of the project.

Besides these planned objectives, supplementary training actions are incorporated to integrate in a coordinated way all initiatives, further adding value in expanding BWS objectives, benefits, and knowledge, both to those directly involved in the project and to a vaster public as well.

1.2 Principles of the training portfolio

The training portfolio comprises a collection of training actions to respond to the set objectives in a tangible way. During the project, the training activities support the developments; at the end of the project, the final portfolio (D1.6 – Final portfolio of training actions) will include the validated set of training activities to ensure capacity building on the water-smart solutions and products and optimise their value.

Relevant principles to building the portfolio are:

- Respond to training needs and expected outcomes, as expressed by partners and stakeholders.
- Incorporate project training actions in a shared harmonised plan aligned with project dissemination and exploitation activities.
- Consider target audience profiles, namely partners, LL stakeholders, interested parties not involved in the project.
- Contribute to a component of the regularly curated knowledge portal during and after project conclusion.
- Provide the training and corresponding materials in English, as a common language for European and non-European countries, complemented by translated versions to foster project impact when found adequate.

2 B-WaterSmart training portfolio contents and structure

2.1 The 3-level approach

The approach selected to structure the BWS training portfolio integrates three levels of training actions. The levels are defined as:

Level 1 (L1): short courses on BWS products and solutions (e.g., guidelines, governance, policies, technologies) as included in the GA as the training portfolio backbone.

Level 2 (L2): state-of-the-art and brainstorming sessions on topics relevant to the core objectives and developments of BWS (e.g., brine disposal aligned with issues in WP2, performance assessment approaches as part of WP6 developments). These sessions complement L1 short courses.

Level 3 (L3): thematic webinars outside the work of BWS but on related topics (e.g., promoted by the LL owners).

An example of the L2 initiatives is the first test training action on “Guidance on building a BWS assessment system” as part of the development of the water smartness assessment framework within B-WaterSmart. The learning objectives for participants included to understand and select adequate assessment criteria, metrics, reference values and targets; to interpret the results of the application of an assessment system; to deal with accuracy and reliability issues. Figure 1 provides information about this training event proposal.

B-WaterSmart				Proposed event information			T 1.3			
Completed by: Helena Alegre				Date:	2021-06-17					
Event title: Guidance on building a BWS assessment system				Responsible person	Name:	Helena Alegre				
					Institution:	LNEC				
					Email:	halegre@lneec.pt				
Event level: Level 2: state-of-the-art and brainstorming sessions				Duration	Up to 3 hours	Details on duration	About 1:30			
Intended timing		Project month (PM): PM11	Possible dates (max 3): 2021-07-01; 2021-06-30							
Main target audience		WP2	Notes: Also to WP5 partners; involvement also of all those participating in assessment criteria and metrics definition or selection							
		WP4								
Participants		Minimum: 3 (WP leaders)	Maximum: -	Expected number	Participation fee (€)	0	Number of editions	-		
				out/15						
Language		English		Preferred means	Web-based		Location			
Learning modes		Synchronous	Asynchronous	Details if asynchronous	The live session will be recorded to be made available as asynchronous.					
		Yes	Yes							
List of topics to be addressed		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction to assessment systems (objectives, uses, structure) - How to define assessment criteria - How to define metrics - Data accuracy and reliability: assessment and implications - How to set reference values and targets - Reporting and evaluation of results - Avoiding common mistakes - Hands-on exercise 				Learning objectives			After this training event, participants should be able: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to understand and select adequate assessment criteria, metrics, reference values and targets; - to interpret the results of the application of an assessment system; - to deal with accuracy and reliability issues 	
<small>This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101017711. The publication reflects only the authors' views and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.</small>										

Figure 1: Lisbon Living Lab session fitting on L2 type of action

As an example of the L3 initiatives, Lisbon Living Lab organises a bi-monthly seminar to support the partners' work not only for BWS people but also beyond. These seminars aim at facilitating the integration of BWS into the partners' long-term strategy and activities and allow partners to become more familiar with each other's work, helping to foster durable synergies. Figure 2 illustrates two sessions organised by Lisbon Living Lab.

Figure 2: Lisbon Living Lab session fitting on L3 type of action

For each of the levels of action, the characteristics to be defined include the list of topics to be addressed, the learning objectives, the target audience, and the type of action.

The final training portfolio (D1.6) will include the validated versions of L1 actions and selected L2 and L3 actions. The contents of the portfolio will be more diverse and richer with the L2 and L3 additions.

2.2 Assessing training needs

The training needs for B-WaterSmart solutions and products identified, associated with developments under WP2 (Water-smart technologies and concepts), WP3 (Water-smart applications and data), WP4 (Circular economy value chains) and WP5 (Society, governance, policy), are presented in the project GA and included as L1 actions. Assessment of these needs will be carried out with a survey to be responded to by the mentioned WP teams. In Table 1, the list of technology and data application products under L1 actions is presented. The annex includes a draft content of the L1 short courses (level 1) and the trainee minimum background requirement for each course.

Table 1: BWS technology products and data application products - candidates for L1 actions

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity	T
Technologies Reuse of water and wastewater		
1	Water reclamation protocol for potable water reuse in beverage industry: showcase safe potable water reuse by food & beverage industry compatible with certification by health and environmental authorities, increase industry resilience to climate change by introducing a climate independent water source (Lisbon).	2.4.1
2	High-recovery reverse osmosis: integration in existing drinking water treatment train. Showcase high recovery reverse osmosis as a solution to increase robust water production by decreasing the raw water quality demands for intake in drinking water production, hence increasing regional system resilience. [Description differs from the GA. The version presented here is in line with the one in the request for the first amendment of the GA, approval pending]	2.3.1
3	Effluent reuse for drinking water production: technology demonstration of effluent reuse for drinking water, introducing alternative drinking water resources to increase regional resiliency. Implementation of quality (nutrients and emerging contaminants) and safety (pathogens removal) controls (Flanders).	2.3.2
4	Compact combinatory treatment technologies for industrial water reuse: demonstration of the possibility of extending water reuse at industrial level by applying a chosen multiple treatment sequence (including ultrafiltration, nanofiltration and reverse osmosis) (Venice).	2.6.1
5	Urban water reuse for agriculture: technology demonstration of urban stormwater reuse for agriculture, introducing alternative water resources for irrigation. Implementation of quality (nutrients and emerging contaminants) and safety (removal of pathogens) controls (Flanders).	2.3.2
6	Combined treatment of vapour condensate and milk/whey permeate for reuse in dairy industry: higher stability and flexibility of the process, more efficient and competitive, exportable into markets with high barriers for approval by authorities. Enables quick shift between different qualities fit for different purposes. Better control of hygiene status of treated water through smart monitoring. Lower barrier for approval by health/food authorities (East Frisia).	2.5.1
Technologies Recovery of energy and materials from water and wastewater		
7	Nitrate-selective EDR: separate nitrates from wastewater effluents, manage separately for: nutrient recovery, water reuse in fertigation. Recovery of nutrients in WWTP effluents for irrigation instead of spending energy in eliminating nutrients (Alicante).	2.1.3
8	Brine electro-chlorination: use of brines from RO in tertiary treatment of WWTP, generate hypochlorite for effluent disinfection and membrane cleaning. Lowering dependence in hypochlorite purchased externally, lowering of salinity in brines to be disposed of (Alicante).	2.1.4
9	Ammonia evaporation CEVAP: evaporation and recovery of liquid ammonia from sludge returns. Recovery of nutrients from the sludge to avoid disposal of ammonia-rich sludges. Use of liquid ammonia in DENOX industry (Alicante).	2.1.5
10	Oil & fat co-digestion technology: use of waste from primary treatment to promote co-digestion and increase biomethane generation. Lowering disposal of waste from the WWTP (Alicante).	2.1.1
11	Ammonia recovery from concentrated WWTP streams: pilot phase, optimise anaerobic digestion of mixtures of sludge and liquid special waste, enhance ammonia concentrations before stripping. Demonstration of nutrients recovery by integration at WWTP (Venice).	2.6.2
12	Efficient small-scale biogas production at small WWTP: distributed energy provision from small WWTP will save energy provided by traditional sources (i.e., electricity system), e.g., in thermal energy for domestic and underground heating systems for de-icing of roads (Bodø).	2.2.2
13	Microturbines for energy recovery: use of microturbines to recover energy from the WWTP effluent for internal reuse of the generated energy (Alicante).	2.1.2

Table 1 (cont.): BWS technology products and data application products – candidates for L1 actions

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity	T
	Technologies Smart management of water systems and infrastructure	
14	IoT sensors for infiltration detection: to improve information available for detection of I/I sources in wastewater networks, improved signal transmission and energy solutions (Bodø).	2.2.1
15	Smart water meters for leak detection: demonstration of leak detection and water quality sensors in an integrated solution with microturbine capabilities to generate enough power to transmit auxiliary data from household smart water meters. This gives significantly improved and more distributed information available for leak detection of water supply networks (Bodø).	2.2.1
	Tools Monitoring, negotiation, and decision support tools	
16	Water reuse strategic platform: FIWARE-based Platform based on ENG's Digital Enabler to support standardized/ transferable evaluations and communication among stakeholders for the assessment of economical/ environmentally sustainable water reuse opportunities. Will provide a shared evaluation model to support objective, traced and updatable decisions (Venice).	3.1, 3.7
17	Environment for decision support and selection of alternative courses of action: city and sector prioritization and decision-making environment, based on sets of key analytics, including water, energy, and nutrient balances; performance, risk, and cost analytics. Expressed numerically and graphically on a georeferenced 2D/3D cityscape environment. (Lisbon).	3.5
18	RE-ACTOR: Smart water allocation and negotiation tool for water reuse: real time water quality and risk monitoring to ensure acceptability of the different water end-users and to visualize the economic and environmental benefits of using the water. Engagement of stakeholders in decision-making through simulation of potential water reuse scenarios (Alicante).	3.2
19	Sludge management platform: based on ENG's Digital Enabler, development of FIWARE-based Platform to support the identification of the optimum sewer sludge valorisation system, to foster energy and resource reuse/recovery. Platform will allow evaluation and ranking of treatment options, considering geographical, environmental, economic, social, and political barriers (Venice).	3.7
20	Urban water cycle (UWC) observatory: tool to develop balances for urban water/resource management, integrating data from different water sources (availability, use, losses, nutrient flow) and creating datasets for multiple users (e.g., municipalities, researchers, water utilities) (Lisbon).	3.5
21	Stormwater reuse management system: system combining operational management of a stormwater basin and a connected sub-irrigation system for groundwater recharge and direct irrigation; optimises system functioning, based on real time data and model predictions (Flanders).	3.4
	Tools Water cycle modelling and assessment tools	
22	UWOT: model for simulation of the urban water cycle from source-to-treatment-to-tap: UWOT will be extended as part of the Responsible Reuse Framework and the Regional Demand-Supply Matching GIS Tool, acting as an urban water cycle simulation engine for both, to explore alternative scenarios for reuse for changing scales, climatic conditions, and legal/ environmental requirements (Flanders, East Frisia).	3.4, 3.6
23	Regional demand-supply matching GIS tool: tool for GIS-based analysis of optimal demand-resource patterns, to identify communal and industrial water requirements and matching with available water resources, calculating, where necessary, transport and treatment requirements. The UWOT model allows to simulate alternative demand & supply options for climate and demand scenarios to rate the resistance of partially decentralized water supply systems (East Frisia).	3.6
24	Reclaimed water distribution network water quality model: hydraulic and water quality modelling of reclaimed water distribution network, capable of exporting files to Epanet and incorporating sensor data (e.g., chlorine residuals, temperature, turbidity, pH). Compatible with other Baseform modules in the project. (Lisbon).	3.5
25	Water-energy-P balance planning module: module for planning support, extending network water and energy balance analytics to include P balance, mapping supply-demand and alternative sources. Compatible with other Baseform modules in the project (Lisbon).	3.5

Table 1 (cont.): BWS technology products and data application products – candidates for L1 actions

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity	T
	Tools Risk assessment tools	
26	QMRA+: Quantitative microbial risk assessment for water reuse and agriculture: expansion of AquaNes tool QMRA for drinking water, for application of water reuse and in agriculture (Flanders).	3.4
27	RA-Reuse: Risk assessment for urban reuse module: tool based on European regulation and ISO standards to facilitate risk assessment and management for safe water reuse. Deals with health and environmental (surface and ground water) risks (Lisbon).	3.5
	Tools Water demand analysis and natural resource management tools	
28	Short-term demand forecasting tool: calculates a high discretization of water demand analyses and allocation of water resources, based on smart meter data (East Frisia).	3.6
29	iWidget+ Platform online platform for water information at utility and customers premises: better information (flow, pressure, temperature, quality) available for leak detection of water supply networks as well as demand management. Builds on past EU projects and delivers a modular FIWARE enabled multi-dashboard (Bodø).	3.3
30	iWidget+ Platform online platform about I/I for wastewater networks: better information (energy provision, signal transmission, information management) available for detection of I/I sources in wastewater networks. Delivers a modular FIWARE enabled multi-dashboard (Bodø).	3.3
31	ASR-pro tool: predicting water quality after subsurface storage: easy to use hydro-chemical tool for fast prediction of water quality after ASR (Flanders).	3.4
	Tools Enabling technology	
32	Digital enabler: integrated digital support system to enable RR and CE at regional scale: evolve the Digital Enabler Platform from Smart City market from smart agriculture and industry to include water domain. FIWARE based Internet of Everything platform (Venice).	3.7
	Tools Other	
33	Climate readiness certification tool: combine water & energy efficiency (incl. simulator & app). Water/energy efficiency certificates and calibration in pilot municipal facilities/housing (Lisbon).	3.5
34	Water smartness assessment framework and tool: a tool to assess the overall gain in water-smartness and sustainability for the LL. Advanced visualisation techniques provide a gamified immersive environment for users to interact with the framework (all LL).	3.9

Planning of training at L2 (state-of-the-art and brainstorming sessions) and L3 (thematic webinars) levels allows more flexibility but ought to be defined, using periodic surveys to partners, to ensure proper planning and divulging. Biannual plans are the basis for these actions, but it is possible to fit in actions planned with shorter notice, schedule permitting.

3 First schedule of training actions

The first schedule of the training actions provides a broad and preliminary calendar for the periods when the different training actions will take place (Figure 3).

For level 1 training actions, the first schedule basis is the project timeline as presented in deliverable D1.7 (Schmuck and Wencki, 2021). Flexibility to accommodate specific products development phases and avoiding an undesirable concentration of training actions in the schedule is achieved by assuming two rounds. These rounds correspond to different products. The first round during a full year is for those BWS products expected to be available earlier, typically after the first quarter of the project's second year and the start of the third year (2022). The second round is mainly for products with longer development and pilot implementation periods. Given the number of products, this division in two rounds allows avoiding the concentration of short courses for the same targets. Replication of training is also planned as required. Subsequent courses can benefit from additional quality control actions.

For level 2 and 3 training actions, the schedule is more flexible, allowing for shorter planning time for organisers but enough time for those who want to benefit from a plan set ahead in time, typically up to six months, and dissemination on the BWS website and other project dissemination resources.

This timeline is coordinated with other project activities (e.g., activities for exploitation and route to the market), where workshops with training aspects at promising new application sites outside the LL are envisaged for M33 to M38, enabling utilization of produced training materials.

The consistency of the training timeline with other activities planned under BWS communication, exploitation and replication activities will be verified regularly during the project development.

Figure 3: B-WaterSmart first training actions schedule: L1 (top); L2 and L3 (bottom)

4 B-WaterSmart training actions workflow and guidance

4.1 Planning the BWS training actions

Planning the BWS training actions involves the collaboration of partners responsible or willing to organise a short course, state-of-the-art presentations, brainstorming sessions, or thematic webinars. Together with the T1.3 and WP7 teams, main workflows, guidance, and quality control will be progressively improved to maximise the benefits of the training actions during the project and beyond.

In the following section, some guidance is provided. Further developments up to M16 (December 2021) include quality control guidance, presentation templates and the basic structure of the short training course.

4.2 BWS training action workflow

For each action, the workflow involving the T1.3 team and the action organisers are presented in Figure 4. Periodic data gathering by the T1.3 team on planned training actions occurs every six months (see form extract in Figure 2). However, partners can send the completed form as soon as they decide to organise a training action. The required form will be available in Nextcloud®. The organisers will provide participants with a link to ensure anonymous responses in the activity assessment.

Figure 4: B-WaterSmart training actions workflow

Information on building the BWS Training Portfolio

This workbook is a form to collect information on training actions under the BWS project and is intended to build a common schedule for the project to avoid undesired overlaps.

For each event, the "proposed event form" sheet needs to be filled by the event organisation responsible person and sent to the T1.3 team (mcalmeida@lnec.pt).

The T1.3 team confirms the action date after verification.

Currently, three types of actions are identified:

Level 1: short courses on BWS products/solutions (e.g., guidelines, governance, policies, technologies) (as per DoW)

Level 2: state-of-the-art and brainstorming sessions (e.g., brine disposal WP2, performance assessment approaches WP6) (new)

Level 3: thematic webinars outside the work of BWS but on related topics (e.g., promoted by the LL owners such as those suggested by Lisbon LL - CML) (new)

Responsible partner by level 1 actions should preferably provide a first version of the training sessions planned (as perDoW) until September 30th. Please fill one form per action and alter the file name to: T1.3_Data_TA#_#, where the first # refers to the work package number and the second to the action sequence numbering for that WP.

Organisers can send updated versions of the action info up to six months before the set date. The date should be agreed upon up to 5 months before.

For level 2 and 3 training actions, the filled form should be sent to the T1.3 team as soon as possible, preferably not after 1 month before the event.

After the action, for all levels, the report template should be filled and sent to the T1.3 team.

B-WaterSmart **Proposed event information to T1.3**

Completed by:

Event title:

Event level:

Intended timing: Project month (PM) Possible dates (max 3)

Main target audience:

Participants: Minimum: Maximum: Expected number:

Language (English and ...):

Learning modes: Synchronous Asynchronous

List of topics to be addressed:

Date:

Responsible person: Name:
 Institution:
 Email:

Duration: Details on duration:

Notes:

Participation fee (€): Number of editions:

Preferred means:

Location:

Details if asynchronous:

Learning objectives:

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Figure 5: Extracts of the training action data template

4.3 Role of T1.3 team

The T1.3 team is responsible for the following:

- develop and coordinate the training schedule and portfolio building;
- decide on the action dates with organisers taking into account the set action schedule;
- collect the relevant information for each training action;
- develop and make available documentation to support planning of training actions;
- gather the contributions of project partners to the training portfolio;
- provide guidance on quality control to the action organisers;
- develop a L1 presentation templates including general contents about the project, and a typical short course structure with the collaboration of courses organisers;
- develop a guidance document for trainers.

4.4 Role of training action organizers

The training action organizers are responsible for the following:

- register the action in BWS portfolio using the action data template available in the Nextcloud® platform;
- define the action dates together with T1.3 team, taking into account the global training action schedule and action priorities (level 1 actions have higher priority);
- send action information to WP7 team for dissemination and materials for asynchronous training, as applicable;
- organise the action and prepare all the support materials;
- fill the action report using the action report template available in the Nextcloud® and return it to T1.3 team;
- supply the link for action evaluation to the participants;
- collaborate with T1.3 team in the preparation of presentation templates, guidance documents and final BWS training portfolio.

5 Assessment of B-WaterSmart training activities and key performance indicators

The assessment of BWS training activities will take place at the end of each action, using an assessment template developed by T1.3 to be returned by participants, anonymously and voluntarily. The analysis of the results together with the action report form will allow the identification of opportunities for improvement. The report form is to be sent to the T1.3 team after the training. Feedback is provided to the organising team to promote improvement in replications of the action.

These activities contribute to the B-WaterSmart objectives, mainly to objective 1 (BWS O1: enable systemic innovation through CoPs and LL, by co-creating, implementing and strengthening local and regional strategies for water-smartness in coastal Europe, with high transfer potential to national and European scales, and capacity building of society and decision-makers, CoPs, LL & collaborative approach in WP1, addressing a broad range of sectors and scales and matching local challenges with opportunities and solutions) and to objective 8 (BWS O8: boost European and international accessibility and replication, exchange, and uptake of innovations in water management and CE, enabling a benchmarking of solutions and their effect at local, regional and national scales, assessing the transfer potential of solutions, by customising and expanding an existing knowledge portal into activities to connect, communicate and replicate in WP7). The contribution of training can influence two main project key performance indicators, as presented in Table 2, especially on the items highlighted in bold.

Table 2: B-WaterSmart training activities: key performance indicators

Project KPI	Description	Targets
KPI_2: Systemic innovation through capacity building and training > BWS O1	<p>Ensure that the products developed meet stakeholders' needs and expectations. Two metrics are used:</p> <p>KPI_2.1: percentage of webinars receiving at least a '4 in 5' average rate by the participants.</p> <p>KPI_2.2: percentage of problem-owners effectively engaged in the Innovation Alliance with a positive self-assessment.</p>	<p>KPI_1.1: ≥ 80% by M36</p> <p>KPI_1.2: ≥ 80% by M40</p>
KPI_10: Knowledge accessibility and uptake > BWS O8	<p>Provide a web-based and continuously curated knowledge portal for solutions, information, training, and a marketplace for water-smart CE solutions. Three metrics are used:</p> <p>KPI_3.1: Number of individuals registered in the portal.</p> <p>KPI_3.2: Number of organisations registered in the portal.</p> <p>KPI_3.3: long-term business plan & operation model for adoption and curation of the portal, by the European Sector organisation Water Europe beyond the project.</p>	<p>KPI_1.3: ≥ 200 by M36</p> <p>KPI_1.4: ≥ 50 by M36</p> <p>KPI_1.5: 100% by M48</p>

6 References

Rebelo, M., Cardoso, M.A., Alegre, H., Andrews, Lisa, Mooren, Caro, Munaretto, S., Gomes, C., Schmidt, L., Oliveira, R., Melo, M. (2021). *CoP's architecture and stakeholder mapping for each Living Lab*. B-WaterSmart Deliverable D1.1.

Schmuck, A., Wencki, K. (2021). *Description and project planning for each Living Lab*. B-WaterSmart Deliverable D1.7 (Confidential report).

7 Annex: Draft contents of L1 short courses and minimum requirements for trainees

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity
	Technologies Reuse of water and wastewater
1	<p>Water reclamation protocol for potable water reuse in beverage industry: showcase safe potable water reuse by food & beverage industry compatible with certification by health and environmental authorities, increase industry resilience to climate change by introducing a climate independent water source (Lisbon).</p> <p>Leading partner Águas do Tejo Atlântico (AdTA) with the cooperation of LNEC.</p> <p>Draft contents</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water quality guidelines, comprising the minimum requirements for monitoring of physical-chemical and microbiological parameters in the reclaimed water. • Fundamentals, mechanisms and key operating conditions and parameters of ozonation and reverse osmosis for advanced wastewater treatment for safe water reclamation & reuse. • Ozonation and reverse osmosis operational guidelines, which includes the (i) start-up of the treatment facility, (ii) validation/optimization of operational parameters and of clean-in-place (CIP) routines, (iii) validation monitoring of the performance targets (incl. microbial and chemical contaminants of emerging concern), (iv) regular operation & maintenance and water quality monitoring. <p>Minimum competences requirements for trainees Knowledge on water/wastewater treatment or on water quality.</p>

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity
	Technologies Reuse of water and wastewater
2	<p>High-recovery reverse osmosis: integration in existing drinking water treatment train. Showcase high recovery reverse osmosis as a solution to increase robust water production by decreasing the raw water quality demands for intake in drinking water production, hence increasing regional system resilience. [Description differs from the GA. The version presented here is in line with the one in the request for the first amendment of the GA, approval pending].</p> <p>See table #3.</p>

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity
	Technologies and tools Solutions for alternative water sources and their potential contribution to a more robust and climate-proof water system (training activities of #2, #3 and #5 ¹)
	<p>2. High-recovery reverse osmosis: integration in existing drinking water treatment train. Showcase high recovery reverse osmosis as a solution to increase robust water production by decreasing the raw water quality demands for intake in drinking water production, hence increasing regional system resilience. [Description differs from the GA. The version presented here is in line with the one in the request for the first amendment of the GA, approval pending].</p> <p>3. Effluent reuse for drinking water production: technology demonstration of effluent reuse for drinking water, introducing alternative drinking water resources to increase regional resiliency. Implementation of quality (nutrients and emerging contaminants) and safety (pathogens removal) controls (Flanders).</p> <p>5. Urban water reuse for agriculture: technology demonstration of urban stormwater reuse for agriculture, introducing alternative water resources for irrigation. Implementation of quality (nutrients and emerging contaminants) and safety (removal of pathogens) controls (Flanders).</p>
	<p>Leading partner</p> <p>KWR (De Watergroep, Aquafin, Proef, Mechelen, Vito)</p>
2, 3 & 5	<p>Draft contents</p> <p>In this training the approach, results and findings from the demonstration site will be shared and put in their regional context. Different options to improve water system robustness will be shared. These include expanding drinking water treatment capacity with advanced purification systems, the potential and basic requirements for effluent reuse for drinking water, as well as options for rainwater reuse for irrigation to address water demand for farmers and reduce pressure on groundwater. The technical demonstrations will be connected to the results of the modelling and tool development (#21, #22, #26, #31) to show how they can contribute to smart water solutions. The objective of this training is to give attendees insight into different options for the implementation alternative water sources, their requirements and key success factors, and their potential to contribute to solving water challenges for the region.</p> <p>The training will have a webinar format.</p>
	<p>Minimum competences requirements for trainees</p> <p>The training is targeted at water professionals and water managers.</p>

¹ Technologies #2, #3 and #5 have been combined into one training activity. This training activity will also be related with the tools #21, #22, #26, #31.

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity
	Technologies Reuse of water and wastewater
	Compact combinatory treatment technologies for industrial water reuse: demonstration of the possibility of extending water reuse at industrial level by applying a chosen multiple treatment sequence (including ultrafiltration, nanofiltration and reverse osmosis) (Venice).
	Leading partner VERI/HYDRO
4	<p>Draft contents</p> <p>Webinar/online short course including the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main objectives of the technology. • Technology overview: how and where. • Our demonstration: goals, different qualities of water investigation for minimal treatment chain individuation, quality suitability in relation to destination, end-users' attitude towards the recovered product. • Balances and carbon footprint evaluations. • Opportunities and limits of the technology (other applications). <p>Intended timing: late 2023. Duration: 2-3 hours.</p> <p>Target audience: decision makers for products exploitation and technology selling/adoption, specifically authorities, utilities, sectoral associations (industrial associations) and end-users, research community and other stakeholders directly/indirectly involved in the production and supply chain.</p> <p>The content of the training will be tailored according to the progress of the activity in terms of feasibility, advantages and barriers identified.</p>
	<p>Minimum competences requirements for trainees</p> <p>Basic knowledge on conventional wastewater treatment processes.</p>

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity
	Technologies Reuse of water and wastewater
5	<p>Urban water reuse for agriculture: technology demonstration of urban stormwater reuse for agriculture, introducing alternative water resources for irrigation. Implementation of quality (nutrients and emerging contaminants) and safety (removal of pathogens) controls (Flanders).</p> <p>Training will be integrated with #3 and #21. See table #3.</p>

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity
	Technologies Reuse of water and wastewater
	<p>Combined treatment of vapour condensate and milk/whey permeate for reuse in dairy industry: higher stability and flexibility of the process, more efficient and competitive, exportable into markets with high barriers for approval by authorities. Enables quick shift between different qualities fit for different purposes. Better control of hygiene status of treated water through smart monitoring. Lower barrier for approval by health/food authorities (East Frisia).</p>
	<p>Leading partner IWW (with contributions from OOWV, DMK and ENV)</p>
6	<p>Draft contents Webinars (one for international audience, one for German audience; approx. 2 hours each) consisting of 3 presentations on the following topics:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Potential of water reuse in the dairy industry: overview of vapour condensate treatment technologies (e.g., incl. virtual tour of pilot plant). 2. Strategies to control and optimise the performance and stability of the process. <p>Digital plant management: potential use for maintenance and process monitoring (e.g., WaterExpert etc.).</p>
	<p>Minimum competences requirements for trainees The training is targeting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dairy processing industry staff (e.g., environmental officers from other producers). • (Future) operators of water recycling plants. • Technology developers. • Representatives of authorities. <p>with basic education in water treatment/wastewater treatment: engineering/science background.</p>

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity
	Technologies Recovery of energy and materials from water and wastewater (training activities of #7 and #8 ²)
	<p>7. Nitrate-selective EDR: separate nitrates from wastewater effluents, manage separately for: nutrient recovery, water reuse in fertigation. Recovery of nutrients in WWTP effluents for irrigation instead of spending energy in eliminating nutrients (Alicante).</p> <p>8. Brine electro-chlorination: use of brines from RO in tertiary treatment of WWTP, generate hypochlorite for effluent disinfection and membrane cleaning. Lowering dependence in hypochlorite purchased externally, lowering of salinity in brines to be disposed of (Alicante).</p>
7 & 8	<p>Leading partner CETAQUA</p>
	<p>Draft contents</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context: brines management. • Brine minimisation and valorisation routes. • SED + EC: The B-WaterSmart circular approach. • Expected benefits.
	<p>Minimum competences requirements for trainees Knowledge on water treatment technologies and basic knowledge on membrane processes. BSc in chemical engineering, environmental science, or related fields.</p>

² Technologies #6 and #7 have been combined into one training activity according to the LL partners.

# Technology / tool / demonstration activity	
	Technologies Recovery of energy and materials from water and wastewater
8	<p>Brine electro-chlorination: use of brines from RO in tertiary treatment of WWTP, generate hypochlorite for effluent disinfection and membrane cleaning. Lowering dependence in hypochlorite purchased externally, lowering of salinity in brines to be disposed of (Alicante).</p> <p>See table #7.</p>

# Technology / tool / demonstration activity	
	Technologies Recovery of energy and materials from water and wastewater
9	<p>Ammonia evaporation CEVAP: evaporation and recovery of liquid ammonia from sludge returns. Recovery of nutrients from the sludge to avoid disposal of ammonia-rich sludges. Use of liquid ammonia in DENOX industry (Alicante).</p> <p>Leading partner CETAQUA</p> <p>Draft contents</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context. Nutrients in WWTPs: impact and potential. • CEVAP Low Thermal evaporator. • Integration of the solution in Alicante. <p>Minimum competences requirements for trainees Knowledge on water treatment technologies. BSc in chemical engineering, environmental science, or related fields.</p>

# Technology / tool / demonstration activity	
	Technologies Recovery of energy and materials from water and wastewater
10	<p>Oil & fat co-digestion technology: use of waste from primary treatment to promote co-digestion and increase biomethane generation. Lowering disposal of waste from the WWTP (Alicante).</p> <p>Leading partner CETAQUA</p> <p>Draft contents</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Theoretical background. • Co-substrates identification and characterisation. • Environmental and economic assessment of the Alicante solution. <p>Minimum competences requirements for trainees Knowledge on wastewater treatment or biological processes.</p>

# Technology / tool / demonstration activity	
	Technologies Recovery of energy and materials from water and wastewater
	Ammonia recovery from concentrated WWTP streams: pilot phase, optimise anaerobic digestion of mixtures of sludge and liquid special waste, enhance ammonia concentrations before stripping. Demonstration of nutrients recovery by integration at WWTP (Venice).
	Leading partner VERI/ETRA/DEPU
11	<p>Draft contents</p> <p>Webinar/online short course including the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main objectives of the technologies (stripping A+C). • Technologies overview: how and where. • Our demonstration: goals, ammonium sulphate salt potentialities as fertilizer, technologies comparison (stripping A vs. stripping C), end-users' attitude towards the recovered product. • Balances and carbon footprint evaluations. • Potential opportunities for CE and limits. <p>Intended timing: late 2023. Duration: 2-3 hours.</p> <p>Target audience: decision makers for products exploitation and technology selling/adoption, specifically authorities, utilities, sectoral associations (agricultural and industrial associations) and end-users, research community and other stakeholders directly/indirectly involved in the production and supply chain.</p> <p>The content of the training will be tailored according to the progress of the activity in terms of feasibility, advantages and barriers identified.</p>
	<p>Minimum competences requirements for trainees</p> <p>Basic knowledge on conventional wastewater treatment processes</p>

# Technology / tool / demonstration activity	
	Technologies Recovery of energy and materials from water and wastewater
	Efficient small-scale biogas production at small WWTP: distributed energy provision from small WWTP will save energy provided by traditional sources (i.e., electricity system), e.g., in thermal energy for domestic and underground heating systems for de-icing of roads (Bodø).
	Leading partner KRKA and SINTEF
12	<p>Draft contents</p> <p>This course is designed with the objective of enriching the technical knowledge for those who are working in the field of energy production, wastewater treatment, municipal planner, etc. and renewable energy enthusiasts and environmentalists. The topics include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Renewable energy: practical introduction to biogás. 2. Key processes: biogas production, possible co-substrates, operation, management of a biogas plant. 3. Overview of different applications of biogás. 4. Biogas in a circular economy (Examples from case studies).
	<p>Minimum competences requirements for trainees</p> <p>Basic knowledge on wastewater plant operation, some understanding of biochemistry and microbiology; Interest in renewable energy.</p>

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity
	Technologies Recovery of energy and materials from water and wastewater
13	Microturbines for energy recovery: use of microturbines to recover energy from the WWTP effluent for internal reuse of the generated energy (Alicante).
	Leading partner Turbulent
	Draft contents <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basics: Hydropower. • Technical design of the solution. • Case studies and application on WWTP.
	Minimum competences requirements for trainees Basic knowledge on hydraulics.

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity
	Technologies Smart management of water systems and infrastructure
14 & 15	14. IoT sensors for infiltration detection: to improve information available for detection of I/I sources in wastewater networks, improved signal transmission and energy solutions (Bodø).
	15. Smart water meters for leak detection: demonstration of leak detection and water quality sensors in an integrated solution with microturbine capabilities to generate enough power to transmit auxiliary data from household smart water meters. This gives significantly improved and more distributed information available for leak detection of water supply networks (Bodø).
	Leading partner NTNU, Techni
	Draft contents <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Necessity of management of infiltration/inflow into the sewage network. • Importance of leak detection and management in water networks. • Smart monitoring of urban water systems. • Introduction to Internet of Things (IoT Basics): application in urban water systems.
	Minimum competences requirements for trainees Basic knowledge and skills in designing and operation of drainage/wastewater and water systems.

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity
	Technologies Smart management of water systems and infrastructure
15	Smart water meters for leak detection: demonstration of leak detection and water quality sensors in an integrated solution with microturbine capabilities to generate enough power to transmit auxiliary data from household smart water meters. This gives significantly improved and more distributed information available for leak detection of water supply networks (Bodø).
	See table #14.

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity
	Tools Monitoring, negotiation, and decision support tools
	Water reuse strategic platform: FIWARE-based Platform based on ENG's Digital Enabler to support standardized/ transferable evaluations and communication among stakeholders for the assessment of economical/ environmentally sustainable water reuse opportunities. Will provide a shared evaluation model to support objective, traced and updatable decisions (Venice).
	Leading partner VERI/ENG
16	Draft contents² Training includes the following topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An overview presentation of the water reuse strategic platform, introducing the users to its contents and functionalities. • A hands-on training presentation serving as a step-by-step guide to use the different functionalities of the Water reuse strategic platform. • Recorded webinars/live demo or screencasts demonstrating scenarios of use of interest to the target audience will be presented.
	Minimum competences requirements for trainees <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competence on using web browsers and web applications. • Background related to water management and the related processes is a plus.

² Components of #32 - Digital Enabler are used to develop the two platforms of the Venice LL (#16 Water reuse strategic platform and #19 Sludge management platform). Training will be delivered for those two platforms and thus there is no need to provide separate training on the Digital Enabler (#32).

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity
	Tools Monitoring, negotiation, and decision support tools
	Environment for decision support and selection of alternative courses of action: city and sector prioritization and decision-making environment, based on sets of key analytics, including water, energy, and nutrient balances; performance, risk, and cost analytics. Expressed numerically and graphically on a georeferenced 2D/3D cityscape environment. (Lisbon).
	Leading partner Baseform
17	Draft contents <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction to the tool's objectives, inputs, and outcomes. 2. Introduction to the operating environment and overview of the user interface. 3. Configuring analysis settings and understanding decision-making basics. 4. Running an analysis and examining results. 5. Exporting results.
	Minimum competences requirements for trainees <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic knowledge of water, energy, and nutrients balances. • Basic knowledge of reused water management.

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity
	Tools Monitoring, negotiation, and decision support tools
	RE-ACTOR: Smart water allocation and negotiation tool for water reuse: real time water quality and risk monitoring to ensure acceptability of the different water end-users and to visualize the economic and environmental benefits of using the water. Engagement of stakeholders in decision-making through simulation of potential water reuse scenarios (Alicante).
	Leading partner CETAQUA / AMAEM
18	Draft contents <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Log-in and basic features of the tool. • Architecture of the tool. • Creation of a baseline scenario. • Creation of results scenarios. • Impact assessment and results interpretation. • Administration role: parameters modification.
	Minimum competences requirements for trainees <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competence on using PCs with Windows and web-apps. • Background related to (urban) water management and related processes (studies in engineering, hydrology, environmental systems, geology and chemistry, urban development and planning etc.) is a plus.

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity
	Tools Monitoring, negotiation, and decision support tools
	Sludge management platform: based on ENG's Digital Enabler, development of FIWARE-based Platform to support the identification of the optimum sewer sludge valorisation system, to foster energy and resource reuse/recovery. Platform will allow evaluation and ranking of treatment options, considering geographical, environmental, economic, social, and political barriers (Venice).
	Leading partner VERI/ENG
19	Draft contents³ Training includes the following topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An overview presentation of the Sludge management platform, introducing the users to its contents and functionalities. • A hands-on training presentation serving as a step-by-step guide to use the different functionalities of the Sludge management platform.
	Recorded webinars/live demo or screencasts demonstrating scenarios of use of interest to the target audience.
	Minimum competences requirements for trainees <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competence on using web browsers and web applications. • Background related to sludge management and the related processes is a plus.

³ Components of #32 - Digital Enabler are used to develop the two platforms of the Venice LL (#16 Water reuse strategic platform and #19 Sludge management platform). Training will be delivered for those two platforms and thus there is no need to provide separate training on the Digital Enabler (#32).

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity
	Tools Monitoring, negotiation, and decision support tools
	<p>Urban water cycle (UWC) observatory: tool to develop balances for urban water/resource management, integrating data from different water sources (availability, use, losses, nutrient flow) and creating datasets for multiple users (e.g., municipalities, researchers, water utilities) (Lisbon).</p> <p>The tool is a visualization instrument for monitoring and communicating performance, support urban planning and decision making. The observatory follows the motto “to know so to reduce”. The tool is divided into two accesses. A public area with open data information of the water and wastewater city dimensions and a private area for individual entities allowing each of them to integrate and analyse, via a set of data analytics, the water consumption of their facilities.</p>
20	<p>Leading partner Lisboa E-Nova</p>
	<p>Draft contents</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An overview presentation of the UWC Observatory, introducing the users to its content and role. • Recorded webinars/live demo and screencast demonstrating the tool and its features.
	<p>Minimum competences requirements for trainees</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competence on using personal computers with Windows. • Updated browser (except internet explorer). • Familiarity with XLS, CSV, PDF, PNG. • Basic knowledge of water consumption units.

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity	T
	Tools Monitoring, negotiation, and decision support tools	
	<p>Stormwater reuse management system: system combining operational management of a stormwater basin and a connected sub-irrigation system for groundwater recharge and direct irrigation; optimises system functioning, based on real time data and rainfall forecasts (Flanders).</p>	
	<p>Leading partner AQUAFIN/ VITO</p>	
21	<p>Draft contents</p> <p>This training will be a demo-session of the stormwater management tool for future operators of the stormwater reuse system. Content will depend on the final operability of the storm water management tool, but can include for example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User guidelines for future operators. • Reflections on potential use cases. • Hands-on demo of the local and remote-control functions of the system, covering both normal system. state and anticipated failure scenarios. 	
	<p>Minimum competences requirements for trainees</p> <p>The training & demo are targeted at operators of (waste)water infrastructure and, where concerned, stakeholders interested in the internal workings of the control, e.g., the municipality.</p> <p>Basic experience of controlled systems and the handling of SCADA-systems is desirable.</p> <p>Basic experience in the interpretation of monitoring data within a hydraulic/hydrologic context is a plus.</p>	

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity	T
	Tools Water cycle modelling and assessment tools	
22	<p>UWOT: model for simulation of the urban water cycle from source-to-treatment-to-tap: UWOT will be extended as part of the Responsible Reuse Framework and the Regional Demand-Supply Matching GIS Tool, acting as an urban water cycle simulation engine for both, to explore alternative scenarios for reuse for changing scales, climatic conditions, and legal/ environmental requirements (Flanders, East Frisia).</p>	
	<p>Leading partner ICCS / KWR</p>	
	<p>Draft contents Training includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An overview presentation of UWOT model introducing the users to its content and role, explaining the way it works and providing results of its application to case studies and insights from past projects. • A UWOT short guide and FAQ on installation and usage along with the most typical issues and their solutions. • A UWOT hands-on training presentation serving as a step-by-step guide to create a topology and run a simulation using UWOT model. • Demo timeseries of UWOT model to perform the hands-on training. • Recorded webinars/live demo or screencasts demonstrating scenarios of use of interest to the target audience. 	
	<p>Minimum competences requirements for trainees</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competence on using PCs with Windows. • Familiarity with MS Office tools, particularly Excel. • Basic knowledge of handling delimited text files (e.g., using Notepad). • Background related to (urban) water management and related processes (studies in engineering, hydrology, environmental systems, geology and chemistry, urban development and planning etc.) is a plus. 	

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity	T
	Tools Water cycle modelling and assessment tools	
23	<p>Regional demand-supply matching GIS tool: tool for GIS-based analysis of optimal demand-resource patterns, to identify communal and industrial water requirements and matching with available water resources, calculating, where necessary, transport and treatment requirements. The UWOT model allows to simulate alternative demand & supply options for climate and demand scenarios to rate the resistance of partially decentralized water supply systems (East Frisia).</p> <p>Leading partner IWW (with contributions from OOWV)</p> <p>Draft contents Webinar (approx. 2,5 hours) consisting of presentations and demonstrations on the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to target application areas and main functionalities of the tool. • High level overview of the tool architecture. • Deep dive into data requirements and (possible) open access data sources. • Demo: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. How to customize the tool to your own case study. b. Use case examples from LL East Frisia. <p>Minimum competences requirements for trainees</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic knowledge in handling GIS data (e.g., shape file) and working with GIS tools. • Background related to water resources management and the related processes (studies in engineering, hydrology, environmental systems, geology and chemistry, urban development and planning etc.) is a plus. 	

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity	T
	Tools Water cycle modelling and assessment tools	
24	<p>Reclaimed water distribution network water quality model: hydraulic and water quality modelling of reclaimed water distribution network, capable of exporting files to Epanet and incorporating sensor data (e.g., chlorine residuals, temperature, turbidity, pH). Compatible with other Baseform modules in the project. (Lisbon).</p> <p>Leading partner Baseform</p> <p>Draft contents</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction to the tool's objectives, inputs, and outcomes. 2. Introduction to the operating environment and overview of the user interface. 3. Configuring input files. 4. Running the analysis. 5. Examining results in the software. 6. Exporting results to common formats. <p>Minimum competences requirements for trainees</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hydraulic models of water distribution systems. • Basic knowledge of the kinetics of waterborne substances in pressure flow. 	

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity	T
	Tools Water cycle modelling and assessment tools	
	Water-energy-P balance planning module: module for planning support, extending network water and energy balance analytics to include P balance, mapping supply-demand and alternative sources. Compatible with other Baseform modules in the project (Lisbon).	
	Leading partner Baseform	
25	Draft contents <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction to the tool's objectives, inputs, and outcomes. 2. Introduction to the operating environment and overview of the user interface. 3. Configuring input files and analysis settings. 4. Running an analysis; exploring alternatives and understanding balances: water, energy, nutrients. 5. Examining results in the software. 6. Exporting results. 	
	Minimum competences requirements for trainees <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic knowledge of water, energy, and nutrients balances. • Basic knowledge of reused water management. 	

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity	T
	Tools Risk assessment tools	
	QMRA+: Quantitative microbial risk assessment for water reuse and agriculture: expansion of AquaNes tool QMRA for drinking water, for application of water reuse and in agriculture (Flanders).	
	Leading partner KWR	
26	Draft contents <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflection and recommendation on the use of the tool and integration of its results in determining purification requirements for water reuse will be included in the training under #3. • User guidelines are available as part of the reporting from the AquaNes project and will be updated where relevant. 	
	Minimum competences requirements for trainees It is recommended to only use this tool with the guidance of a qualified expert in microbial water safety planning.	

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity	T
	Tools Risk assessment tools	
	<p>RA-Reuse: Risk assessment for urban reuse module: tool based on European regulation and ISO standards to facilitate risk assessment and management for safe water reuse. Deals with health and environmental (surface and ground water) risks (Lisbon).</p>	
	<p>Leading partner Baseform</p>	
27	<p>Draft contents</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction to the tool's objectives, inputs, and outcomes. 2. Introduction to the operating environment and overview of the user interface. 3. Configuring analysis settings and understanding help resources. 4. Running an analysis: human risk and environmental risk. 5. Examining results in the software and revising analysis settings for sensitivity analysis. 6. Submitting final scores; running a definitive analysis. 7. Exporting results. 	
	<p>Minimum competences requirements for trainees</p> <p>Familiarity with ISO standards (TC 282 Water Reuse):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISO 16075 Guidelines for treated wastewater use for irrigation projects (2020, 2021); • ISO 20426:2018 Guidelines for health risk assessment and management for non-potable water reuse; • ISO 20761:2018 Guidelines for water reuse safety evaluation. <p>Familiarity with EU regulation (EU) 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 May 2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse.</p>	

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity	T
	Tools Water demand analysis and natural resource management tools	
	<p>Short-term demand forecasting tool: calculates a high discretization of water demand analyses and allocation of water resources, based on smart meter data (East Frisia).</p>	
	<p>Leading partner IWW (with contributions from OOWV)</p>	
28	<p>Draft contents</p> <p>Webinar (approx. 2 hours) consisting of presentations and demonstrations on the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation: Motivation and functionality of the tool. • Presentation: High level overview of the tool architecture (frontend, backend, smart meters, FIWARE components). • Demo: how to interact with the frontend to create forecasting models and using them for generating short-term demand forecasts. 	
	<p>Minimum competences requirements for trainees</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competence on using a web browser. • Basic data interpretation skills / good understanding of data (e.g., familiarity with the concept of time series data). 	

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity	T
	Tools Water demand analysis and natural resource management tools	
	Nessie system: better information at a householder level (e.g., flow, pressure, temperature, quality) available for leak detection of water supply networks as well as demand management. Builds on past EU projects and delivers a modular FIWARE enabled multi-dashboard (Bodø) ⁴ .	
	Leading partner ICCS	
29	Draft contents Training includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An overview presentation of Nessie system introducing the system, explaining the way it works and providing results of its application to case studies and insights from past projects. • Session using recorded (videos) and live demonstrations of implementations of the system from past projects. Training material includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guide to explain the features of API of the system which allow third-party applications (models, analytics) to integrate with the system and exchange data. 	
	Minimum competences requirements for trainees <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competence on using personal computers and server applications • Background related to (urban) water management and the related processes (studies in engineering, hydrology, environmental systems, geology and chemistry, urban development and planning etc.) is a plus. • Background related to ftp-type communications and application programming interface (API) 	

⁴ Initial developments of Nessie system have been implemented in the iWidget project. The former known as iWidget platform (as described in DoW) gradually evolved into the Nessie system.

#	Technology / tool / demonstration activity	T
	Tools Water demand analysis and natural resource management tools	
	Environmental dashboard⁵: better information (energy provision, signal transmission, information management) available for detection of I/I sources in wastewater networks. Delivers a modular FIWARE enabled multi-dashboard (Bodø).	
	Leading partner NORDKONTAKT	
30	Draft contents Recorded webinars/live demo demonstrating dashboards functionalities with multiple data sources.	
	Minimum competences requirements for trainees Solution will be intuitive, and there will be no need for special prior knowledge.	

⁵ Tool #30 was described in DoW as “iWidget+ Platform (or Fiware enabled multidashboard)” and was renamed to “Environmental Dashboard” during current project development.

# Technology / tool / demonstration activity	
	Tools Water demand analysis and natural resource management tools
	SuTRa: easy to use hydro-chemical tool that helps predict the removal of (plant) pathogens during subsurface storage and transport. The intended use of the tool is to help determine the minimum design parameters for subsurface storage and infiltration solutions (Flanders) ⁶ .
	Leading partner KWR
31	Draft contents <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflection and recommendation on the use of the tool and its use in designing subsurface water storage solutions will be included in the training under #3.to be completed. • User guidelines will be included as part of the reporting on the tool.
	Minimum competences requirements for trainees The tool is targeted for use by hydrologists in research and consulting organizations.

⁶ The tool was formerly known as ASR pro but it was renamed to SuTRa. Additional information has been provided in tool's description (compared to DoW) based on its application to the Flanders LL.

# Technology / tool / demonstration activity	
	Tools Enabling technology
32	Digital enabler: integrated digital support system to enable RR and CE at regional scale: evolve the Digital Enabler Platform from Smart City market from smart agriculture and industry to include water domain. FIWARE based Internet of Everything platform (Venice). See tables #16 and #19.

# Technology / tool / demonstration activity	
	Tools Other
	Climate readiness certification tool: combine water & energy efficiency (incl. simulator & app). Water/energy efficiency certificates and calibration in pilot municipal facilities/housing (Lisbon).
	Leading partner ADENE
33	Draft contents Training includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of the Climate Ready Certificates Methodology, and its usability in the platform. A manual of the methodology application is provided as support material. • Case studies, from the application of the methodology in different pilot's typology (households, buildings, and neighbourhoods).
	Minimum competences requirements for trainees <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competence on using PCs with Windows. • Familiarity with MS Office tools, particularly Excel. • Background related to (urban) water and energy management and the related processes (studies in engineering, energy, sustainability, hydrology, environmental systems, urban development and planning etc.) is a plus.

# Technology / tool / demonstration activity	
	Tools Other
	Water smartness assessment framework and tool: a tool to assess the overall gain in water-smartness and sustainability for the LL.
	Leading partner ICCS
34	Draft contents The training L1 will be organized under the umbrella of WP3, Task 3.9 towards the end of the project; it is envisaged that it will take advantages from the cooperation of WP6 and 3: WP6 will provide information about the concept of the B-WaterSmart assessment framework including examples from the InAll validation experience and the training exercises tailored for the InAll; Task 3.9 will organize the training activity around the dashboard, as the actual product to train about. The training is expected to include presentation of the tool and its functionalities. The exact training content will be decided at the later stage once the developments on the dashboard have started.
	Minimum competences requirements for trainees <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The BWS AF (Water smartness assessment framework) addresses the strategic level of decision makers; further competence requirements related to the provision of data will be defined at later stage. • Competence on using personal computers, additional requirements to be provided at a later stage.

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